

Drying of a Multicomponent Polymeric Coating Film: Modelling and Experiments

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Abstract

The convective drying of a multicomponent polymeric solution containing two volatile components (acetone and ethanol), one non-volatile (cellulose acetate hydrogen phthalate), and an optional non-volatile component (ethylene glycol) as a softener was studied. Experiments were carried-out on a flat thin film geometry in batch mode. A mathematical model was presented to describe the composition profiles in the film as a function of time. Experiments showed that the drying rate exhibits two distinct falling periods. Addition of a softener changed the drying behaviour. Experiments where the softener was present show a higher and faster decrease of evaporation rates during initial stage of the drying process. Physically, the film developed a membrane on the surface at the beginning of the evaporation, becoming thicker as the solvents were depleted. Lateral or edge drying was observed along the exposed evaporation surface. Simulation results have a good qualitative agreement with experiments.

1. Introduction

A step in the manufacture of various products—such as photographic films, magnetic storage media, adhesives, membranes, synthetic fibbers, and coatings—is to apply a thin film of a polymeric solution to provide for additional characteristics that enhanced the quality of such products. The drying of multicomponent polymeric solutions consisting of at least one polymer and one or more solvents is important because of its influence on the quality of the product. For instance, to improve the quality of pharmaceutical products, tablets are coated to provide physical and chemical protection for the drug, to control the release of the drug from the tablet, to mask the taste, odour or colour of the drug, or to simply improve the appearance of the tablet. In another pharmaceutical application, an active substance is embedded in a polymeric film for intradermal-controlled release. In such cases, an even distribution of the active substance will determine the efficiency of its release. Therefore, the simulation of the drying process can be useful to optimise and ensure product quality.

Drying of polymeric solutions has focused mainly on one or two solvents in experimental and modelling approaches. Vrentas and Vrentas [1] provided an analytical solution for the

drying of a binary polymeric solution film using a linear relationship for the concentration dependence of diffusion. They also studied the effects of the solvent's surface concentration on the initial evaporation rate, verifying that an increase of solvent concentration at the surface does not increase solvent removal. Alsoy [2] treated a ternary system limiting the analysis to cases above their glass transition temperature. Yoshida and Miyashita [3] studied the drying of a ternary polymeric solution containing two solvents using both the theory of Vrentas and the Flory-Huggins equation. Dabral *et al.* [4] also studied the drying of a ternary polymeric solution consisting of a solvent and a non-solvent exhibiting phase separation. Vrentas and Vrentas [5] proposed a model for the non-isothermal drying of polymer solutions with shrinking effects. Guerrier *et al.* [6] solved the non-isothermal model for the drying of a binary polymeric solution assuming Fickian diffusion. Yamamura *et al.* [7] studied the evaporation of a ternary polymeric solution containing two polymers presenting primary and secondary phase separations. Wagner and Schlünder [8] studied the drying of a ternary polymeric coating by means of reflective-FTIR concluding that the solvent with the smallest diffusion controls the total evaporation rate.

In this study, a mathematical model for diffusion in a multicomponent liquid film considering that one of the components is non-volatile (in our case a polymer) was presented. The solution of the model was compared with experimental data. Two general cases were considered: (1) a polymeric solution consisting of two volatile liquids and a polymer; and (2) a polymeric solution with two volatile liquids, one non-volatile liquid used as a softener, and a polymer. A softener is usually added to give better mechanical properties to the dried film. The use of a softener in this study is mainly included to see its influence on the evaporation process.

2. Theory

2.1 Diffusion in liquid phase

Diffusion of n species in a single phase is described by the differential equations of continuity for all n components of the mixture. Applied to mass transfer in a liquid film it yields:

$$\frac{\partial(c_l x_i)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (G_t x_i) = -\nabla \cdot J_i \quad (1)$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, x_i is the molar fraction of compound i in the liquid, J_i is the diffusion flux of component i , c_l is the total concentration and G_t the total molar flux. The molar flux G_i , with respect to a stationary coordinate frame of reference, are related to the diffusion fluxes by:

$$G_i = J_i + x_i G_t \quad (2)$$

Because $\sum x_i = 1$ and $\sum J_i = 0$, only $n-1$ equations (1) are independent and an additional condition, specific for a given diffusion problem, is required in order to determine the molar fluxes. This is frequently represented by an interrelationship between the molar fluxes. In addition to initial and boundary conditions, the solution of the set of equations (1) requires a relationship between diffusion fluxes and mole fraction gradients in the system. One of these relationships is provided by a generalisation of Fick's law for binary diffusion. For one-dimensional diffusion, it is expressed in compact matrix notation as follows:

$$\mathbf{J} = -c_l \mathbf{D} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial z} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{D} is the matrix of multicomponent diffusion coefficients. The column vectors of diffusion fluxes and composition gradients have the dimension $n-1$ to match the dimensions of matrix \mathbf{D} , which is of order $n-1 \times n-1$. This expresses the fact that the n th component does not diffuse independently. In non-ideal mixtures, the matrix of multicomponent diffusion coefficients is defined as:

$$\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{B}^{-1} \Gamma \quad (4)$$

The matrix \mathbf{B} , which can be regarded as a kinetic contribution to the multicomponent diffusion coefficients, has the elements:

$$B_{ii} = \frac{x_i}{\mathfrak{D}_{in}} + \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq i}}^n \frac{x_k}{\mathfrak{D}_{ik}} \quad (5)$$

$$B_{ij} (i \neq j) = -x_i \left(\frac{1}{\mathfrak{D}_{ij}} - \frac{1}{\mathfrak{D}_{in}} \right) \quad (6)$$

where $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$ and \mathfrak{D}_{ij} are the Maxwell-Stefan diffusion coefficients. The elements of the matrix of thermodynamic factors, Γ , are given by:

$$\Gamma_{ij} = \delta_{ij} + \frac{x_i}{x_j} \frac{\partial \ln \gamma_i}{\partial \ln x_j} \quad (7)$$

where γ_i is the activity coefficient of compound i and $\delta_{i,j}$ is the Kronecker delta ($\delta_{i,j} = 1$ for $i = j$ and $\delta_{i,j} = 0$ for $i \neq j$). For ideal solutions, the matrix of thermodynamic factors reduces to the identity matrix.

2.2 Mathematical model

Figure 1 shows schematically a film section for the process of drying a polymeric liquid film. The model represents a thin liquid film supported on an inert non-porous solid. The gas flows over the sample serving as a medium to transfer heat to the polymeric film and to carry away vapours.

Fig. 1 Convective drying of a multicomponent polymeric film.

The following assumptions apply to the model: the polymeric coating film is considered to be an homogeneous phase throughout the drying process and diffusion is one-dimensional; the initial concentration is uniform throughout the film; under transient conditions, mass transfer through the film thickness is controlled by diffusion; despite shrinkage, the frame of reference is fixed with respect to the film and its thickness is assumed constant for calculations; no chemical reaction takes place; skinning and edge effects are negligible; the added softener has negligible volatility; and, there is no heat transfer from below.

Combining Equations (1) and (3) for diffusion in one dimension:

$$\frac{\partial(c_l \mathbf{x})}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(c_l \mathbf{D} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial z} \right) - \frac{\partial(G_l \mathbf{x})}{\partial z} \quad (8)$$

If the non-volatile component is labelled as the n th component the total flux can be calculated as:

$$G_l = - \frac{c_l}{x_n} \mathbf{1}^T \mathbf{D} \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dz} \quad (9)$$

Equations (8) allow for the calculation of liquid compositions. To determine the number of moles remaining in the mixture, the mass balances for each species are required:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{N}_l}{dt} = -A\mathbf{G}_v \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{N}_l is the vector of number of moles, A is the evaporation area, and \mathbf{G}_v is the vector of evaporation fluxes. In general, to simulate the evaporation of a multicomponent liquid film will demand the solution of Equations (8) together with an energy balance and respective initial and boundary conditions. For non-isothermal evaporation of a liquid thin film, the energy balance results in:

$$\frac{\partial(c_l c_{pl} T_l)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left\{ k_l \frac{\partial T_l}{\partial z} \right\} - \frac{\partial(G_l c_{pl} T_l)}{\partial z} \quad (11)$$

where T_l is the liquid temperature, c_{pl} is the molar heat capacity and k_l is the thermal conductivity. Equations (8), (10) and (11) constitute a system that combines coupled partial differential equations with an ordinary differential equation. The corresponding initial and boundary conditions are:

$$\text{At } t = 0, 0 \leq z \leq \delta \quad T_l = T_{l0} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{At } z = 0, t > 0 \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial z} = 0; \quad \frac{\partial T_l}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$\text{At } z = \delta, t > 0 \quad c_l \mathbf{D} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial z} = -\mathbf{G}_v; \quad -k_l \frac{\partial T_l}{\partial z} = q_{cv} - \boldsymbol{\lambda}^T \mathbf{G}_v \quad (14)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ is a column vector of heat of vaporisation. The superscript T denotes transposition. The corresponding initial conditions for the total material balance are given by:

$$\text{At } t = 0 \quad \mathbf{N} = \mathbf{N}_0 \quad (15)$$

2.3 Experimental part

Two sets of experiments are performed by drying a thin polymeric solution. The first set consists of a ternary mixture containing two volatile solvents and one non-volatile diluted polymer solid. The second set considers a quaternary mixture containing two volatile solvents, one non-volatile solvent and one non-volatile diluted polymer solid. In the latter set, the non-volatile solvent acts as a softener. The main variables to take into account are the initial concentration of dissolved polymer solid, initial concentrations of volatile and non-volatile solvents, initial liquid temperature, liquid composition, gas temperature, gas composition, and gas velocity.

A schematic arrangement of the experimental setup is shown in Fig. 2. The equipment may be divided into four main sections as follows: gas supply and dehumidification section, heating section, drying chamber, and analysing equipment. The blower B supplies a gas flow—a broad range of flow rates are possible by changing the rpm setting through the frequency converter FC. The air passes through a column DT containing a dehumidificant (silica gel) to obtain a process air of low humidity content (less than 1.0 % relative humidity) measured by a hygrometer (H). The air velocity is measured by an anemometer (A). After dehumidification, the air is pre-heated with electrical resistance heaters (PR) of up to 2 kW each. Temperature is controlled by means of a PID temperature controller (TC) that supplies heat by means of an electrical resistance heater as its final control element. Before entering the drying chamber, the static mixer (SM) homogenises temperature by mixing the gas. At this point, there is an outlet for supplying the reference air to the interferometer. The sample is put in a sample holder (S) inside the drying chamber (D) and is supported on a weighing balance (B) through an oil-sealed shaft.

The sample's weight history is recorded on a computer. At the outlet of the drying chamber the exhausted air (EA) is mixed to get a homogeneous composition. The air sample is passed through a gas cell attached to the infrared spectrometer (IR) where it is analysed. The spectrometer makes an interferometric reading semi-continuously. It is possible to take an interferometric reading every 30 seconds. Post-processing of these readings yields the gas composition. The drying chamber has a uniform cross-sectional area of 90 mm × 110 mm.

Fig. 2 Schematic arrangement of experimental setup.

The physical model consists of a sample holder containing a liquid film mixture of 1 mm thickness. The sample holder is introduced into a drying chamber (see Fig. 2) where the sample dries under controlled conditions. The first system selected is a mixture of ethanol – acetone – cellulose acetate phthalate, a common mixture used to cover pills. The second system additionally contains 1,2-propanediol, non-evaporating liquid, as a fourth component of negligible volatility. In every experimental run the following was determined: initial concentration of polymer; initial concentration of softener, when added; initial concentration of volatiles; initial temperature of liquid sample; and initial weight of liquid sample.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Experimental observations

During the experimental runs, as soon as the film is exposed to the drying gas a thin turbid membrane is observed on the surface of the film. This phenomenon occurs in both types of mixtures, with and without softener. The influence of adding a softener (ethylene glycol in this case) can be seen in Fig. 3, where the evaporation rates of two mixtures are compared at the same experimental conditions. At the beginning, the evaporation process is very fast as shown in Fig. 3. The steep slope in the curves indicates that there is a rapid change in the evaporation fluxes during the first stage of the process. Since a spectrum is measure at fixed intervals, it is likely that the first measurement does not show the concentration of the sudden initial evaporation. Another problem is imposed by the volume cell, which limits measurements to average readings. This sudden evaporation accounts for the instant depletion of the solvents leaving the exposed polymeric film. The drop of concentration at the interface due to the instantaneous evaporation of the solvents in the initial stage of the process, which causes a large concentration gradient, may explain such behaviour.

The membrane formation serves as a surface layer to both the liquid and the gas with elastic properties at the beginning of the evaporation process, while the material underneath is still a liquid. As the evaporation progresses the membrane grows thicker showing solid-like characteristics as the liquid is depleted.

Fig. 3 Effect of softener addition to the polymer solution.

The extent to how much this membrane influences the evaporation will partly depend on how fast it thickens, since the solvents must now diffuse through it to reach the side of the membrane exposed to the gas (gas-membrane interface). The formation of this membrane becomes an additional resistance to mass transfer during evaporation. Edge or lateral drying

is also observed once solvent depletion is in progress, thus forming a dry front which advances inwardly from all exposed sides of the sample.

The presence of the softener helps to increase the evaporation rates. The film with the mixture that contains the softener evaporates faster than the one without softener. This behaviour may be explained by due to the presence of softener molecules in the interstices of the polymer membrane, providing a “wet” way through which solvent molecules can diffuse towards the exposed surface—in contrast to the case where no softener is added, where the exposed surface dries out in the beginning of the evaporation and brings about a severe resistance to mass transfer. Consequently, the presence of the softener may alter the diffusion of the solvent through the membrane in a positive way, thus allowing diffusion to the outer layer.

3.2 Modelling results

Because of the lack of experimental data for the polymer of interest in this study (cellulose acetate hydrogen phthalate, CAP), polymer properties are estimated by using methods found in the literature [9]. For calculation purposes, CAP is modelled as a dimer. In this way, the use of mass fractions is avoided, which are commonly used to express concentrations in polymeric solutions due to the high molecular weight of polymers.

Due to the lack of data and the inherent uncertainties involved in the free-volume approach, the method of Bandrowski and Kubaczka [10] is used to estimate diffusion coefficients, which allows for the calculation of Maxwell-Stefan diffusion coefficients in a wide concentration range. According to this method, the matrix of thermodynamic factors is corrected by an empirical exponent. Other transport properties, such as viscosity and thermal conductivity, are calculated by taking the polymer as a sub-cooled liquid.

For phase equilibrium calculations, the UNIFAC model is used with a modification of the volume parameter suggested by Zhong [11], and modelling the polymer as a dimer. Other parameters are calculated using methods proposed by Reid *et al.* [12] using estimated critical parameters for components, which lack experimental data.

Assuming a flat geometry, mass and heat transfer coefficients at zero mass transfer rates are calculated according to the boundary layer theory for streamline flow and the Chilton-Colburn analogy for turbulent flow. Diffusion coefficients in the gas phase are estimated using the method of Fuller [12]. The bootstrap matrix β is calculated for diffusion through a stationary gas. The matrix of correction factors is calculated using the linearised theory. The differential equations are solved using the method of lines, where the space domain is discretised and the resulting ordinary differential equations are solved with a method of variable-order numerical differentiation formulas.

The concentration profiles in Fig. 4 show a rapid depletion of acetone and an increasing concentration of CAP on the interface. The simulations show a moderate behaviour for acetone, compared to the experimental one, but it still shows faster evaporation of acetone than that of ethanol. From Fig. 4, it is seen that acetone is removed faster from the surface than ethanol, but its diffusion velocity in the polymeric solution is also faster.

Fig. 4 Concentration profiles. Calculations performed at the following conditions:

$$T_l = 298.15 \text{ K}; T_g = 323.15 \text{ K}; u_g = 0.80 \text{ m/s}.$$

Due to the particular components in the mixture, it is expected that the interaction of the solvents and polymer be non-ideal. This is confirmed by the improvement of the agreement between simulations and experimental results when the exponent of the matrix of thermodynamic factors deviates from zero (ideal case), as seen in Fig. 5. Thus, simulations represent the drying process better when no softener is added to the polymer solution, and only qualitatively when there is a softener in the liquid mixture. In Fig. 5, it is also possible to notice that acetone is removed faster than ethanol in the beginning of the evaporation. The molar fraction of ethanol remains almost constant for the first quarter of the evaporation period when no softener is present, while it slightly increases when the softener is present. This may be due to the more polar molecule of ethanol that may associate stronger with CAP chain molecules making it diffuse slower to the membrane interface and consequently it is removed slower than acetone.

Fig. 5 Average liquid molar fraction. Simulations performed at the following conditions:
 $T_l = 298.15 \text{ K}$; $T_g = 323.15 \text{ K}$; $u_g = 0.80 \text{ m/s}$.

The residual coating obtained after all solvents have evaporated had a solid transparent consistency. Samples dried without softener were non-flexible and have a glassy appearance. On the other hand, samples containing softener were flexible to some extent, although still glassy.

4. Conclusions

A model for mass transfer applied to the drying of a multicomponent polymeric solution film has been presented. The model considers the presence of a stagnant component, the polymer, in the liquid. Experiments and simulations are compared to elucidate the extent to which the model can be applied.

Experimental observation shows that a membrane is formed during the initial stage of evaporation when the sample suddenly enters in contact with the hot gas in the drying chamber. This may be explained by the quick depletion of solvents at the beginning of the evaporation process. During this short period of time the membrane remains visually turbid. The membrane later humidifies by the replenishment of solvents at the surface. Then, once a certain regime is established, when the rate of reposition of solvents at the surface is lower than the evaporation rate, the membrane thickens during the rest of the evaporation process.

The presence of an additional non-evaporating component, serving as a softener, affects the evaporation process. It is observed that when a softener is added the evaporation rate during the first falling rate period of the process proceeds faster than in the case where no softener is present. Since the softener remains in the polymeric membrane this may help in the mass transport through the membrane. In this case, the softener affects the evaporation in a positive way (i.e. not hindering evaporation). Depending on the characteristics of the softener substance, results may vary.

Comparison of experimental and simulation results are in good qualitative agreement. Experiments show that acetone is removed preferentially, ethanol remains almost constant during the first part of the drying process, even with a slightly increasing concentration

when a softener substance is added to the mixture. Even though properties are calculated from proven methods, the model can be used up to some extent. Further work should aim at refining this approach and test the model with other polymeric solutions, where the polymer lacks experimental parameters.

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